

What kind of restoration trajectories are expected in riparian zones? Succession and disturbance theoretical perspectives.

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Abstract

Natural river landscapes harbour a high biodiversity due to their high habitat heterogeneity and river connectivity. However, Riverine systems being important landscape components from a holistic conservation perspective, are under great threat worldwide as a consequence of anthropogenic perturbations (e.g. dams, urban areas). As restoration proceeds, there is an excellent opportunity to study the successional dynamics of vegetation development in these newly created riverine ecosystems. However, traditionally two successional theories have been predominant in ecological restoration field; the Clementsian view of succession based on deterministic linear plant species turnover proportional to environmental changes, and the Gleasonian approach also known as “relay floristic” approach which predicted a sequential replacement of species through autogenic facilitation and inhibition interactions. Nowadays, new emerging theoretical frameworks are pushing the interest and practicality of state and transition models as a new way of viewing and managing the effects of disturbance in natural and human-manipulated ecosystems. Here, the advantages and disadvantages of these three successional theories will be discussed, putting the main focus on the design and implementation of management plans to restore degraded riverine systems.

Keywords: Ecological restoration, Community dynamics, Revegetation, Plants, Management.

1. Introduction

The human settlements have been traditionally located close to rivers, consequently riverine ecosystem have been impacted by human activities for centuries. A clear example of these impacts is the loss of natural river landscapes close to cities, which have been transformed in agricultural or urban landscapes through time (Paul & Meyer 2008). Currently, the scale and type of anthropogenic perturbations (e.g. dams, urban areas) and globalization of species pools are worldwide problems that riverine systems need to face (Meiners et al. 2015). Nevertheless, natural river landscapes of the temperate regions can harbour a high biodiversity (plants, birds) due to their high habitat heterogeneity and both lateral and longitudinal river connectivity (Lee et al. 2014). Nowadays, riverine systems being important landscape components from a holistic conservation perspective, are under great threat worldwide, thus their conservation and restoration should be a societal challenge (Lee et al. 2014).

In damaged riverine systems, the aim of the ecological restoration should be to create a healthy, self-sustaining ecosystems, which are similar to semi-natural or natural ecosystems that were present before degradation (SERI 2006). Specifically, focusing on riverbank areas, ecological restoration should be able to create a self-sustaining riparian vegetation community similar to pre-disturbance one. As restoration proceeds, there is an excellent opportunity to study the successional dynamics of vegetation development in these newly created riparian ecosystems (Alday et al. 2011). For example, riparian succession models improve our understanding of vegetation dynamics and trajectories in response to perturbations and restoration programs, being fundamental tools to define achievable restoration goals or to design adaptive restoration practices.

In the last years, there are numerous successional theories that explored how ecosystems respond to disturbances (e.g. Clementsian, Gleasonian, state and transition models). However, in ecological restoration field, and especially when restoring vegetation traditionally two successional theories have been predominant to describe

this process: (a) the Clementsian successional point of view (Clements, 1916) based on deterministic linear plant species turnover proportional to environmental changes (i.e. gradual continuum models), and (b) the Gleasonian approach (Gleason, 1926) also known as “relay floristic” approach which predicted a sequential replacement of species through autogenic facilitation and inhibition interactions. In any case, recent works have been demonstrated that these two successional theories are not always effective in describing restoration outcomes. For example, after the eruption of Mount Sant Hellens (USA) Franklin and MacMahon (2000) found that vegetation recovery do not follow the expected pattern of "ecological succession" from the edges, rather it was found to be highly heterogeneous. At the same time, riparian vegetation restoration plans usually employ site-specific actions to accelerate the successional process complicating predictability of trajectories. Unfortunately, each restoration action has the potential to change the trajectory of ecosystem development in ways that are largely uncharted (Zedler 2000).

As a consequence, new emerging theoretical frameworks, based on alternative states and resilience concepts, have pushed innovative conceptual successional models that can have interesting applications in restoration ecology (Pulsford et al. 2016). For example, the interest and practicality of state and transition models as a new way of viewing and managing the effects of disturbance in natural and human-manipulated ecosystems is increasing (Sudding & Hobbs 2009). Therefore, the identification of different states and ecological thresholds driving species turnover and possibly leading to alternative states can not only inform theories of plant succession, but also the restoration of riparian zones (Bourgeois et al. 2016).

Here, the advantages or disadvantages from a riparian vegetation restoration point of view of the traditional Clementsian and Gleasonian successional theories are reviewed briefly. In contrast, a more detailed description of “state and transition models”, along their applicability to predict riparian vegetation restoration outcomes is given.

2. Successional theories traditional used in ecological restoration

The Clementsian view of succession

The Clementsian view of succession (Clements, 1916) is based on deterministic linear plant species turnover proportional to environmental changes (i.e. gradual continuum models). It always starts from a “bare state” and progressing from pioneer species to a final stage or “climax community” (Pulsford et al. 2016; Figure 1). In each of these stages, the established species modify the environmental conditions, therefore, new conditions enable species from next stages to colonise the areas and outcompete the old species.

Figure 1. Schematic view for a forest ecosystem of the Clementsian succession model.

This is a highly deterministic theory, which determines that vegetation will converge on a climatically determined and predictable stable climax community. Unfortunately, monitoring programs over restoration experiments have demonstrated that the predictability of next stages is not always true (Bourgeois et al. 2016), and most of the times are dependent on successional drivers (Meiners et al. 2015). Nowadays, ecological systems are viewed as dynamics, complex and non-equilibrium in nature (Pulsford et al. 2016). Thus, the complexity of restoring vegetation is not as simple as expected.

In any case, there are still a lot of restoration works planned over this theoretical approach. Here, practitioners assume a linear turnover of planted species which increases the complexity of the ecosystem, and finally previous vegetation community will be restored because of species substitution. In these cases, it is recommended to revisit the area under restoration periodically (e.g every 2 years) to identify whether restoration trajectories follow the desired reference direction or new interventions should be needed to redirect the community trajectory to fit the restoration target objectives (Alday et al. 2011).

The Gleasonian or “relay floristic” approach

The Gleasonian approach (Gleason, 1926) also known as “relay floristic” approach is more complex and less deterministic than Clementsian view of succession. This theory predicted a sequential replacement of species through autogenic facilitation and inhibition interactions (e.g plants and biotic factors; Connell & Slatyer 1977). Therefore, the first organisms to leave the system were those least tolerant to changing environmental conditions (Pulsford et al. 2016).

This is less deterministic theory which considers succession as a no end point process. Practitioners, who planned restoration works using this approach assume two concepts; firstly, that the initial colonizing species will facilitate the later colonization of medium- and late-successional native species through time, and secondly that the resulting restored community will be similar to surrounding native plant communities.

Unfortunately, it should be considered that these succession theories are not accommodated to smaller scale, shorter-term and site-specific patterns (Zedler 2000), neither to isolation or the globalization of species pools (invasive species; Lee et al. 2014). Therefore, usually the restoration outcomes are not those planned or expected.

3. State and transition models applied in ecological restoration

The new theoretical frameworks such as resistance and resilience and alternative states (Holling, 1973; Scheffer et al., 1993) are opening new ways of viewing and managing the effects of disturbance in natural and human-manipulated ecosystems (Westoby et al. 1989). State transition models assume the existence of a number of states in which a system can exist, but there are specific events (disturbances) that can drive systems between alternative states, being these transitions gradual or abrupt.

For example, the theoretical transition model between two communities is represented in Figure 2. Here, management action (orange arrow - disturbance) is planned to change grass dominated community (old state) and restore a riparian vegetation (new state). Therefore, management should overcome the initial resistance and resilience of the degraded grassland community (old state) flipping the ball from its state to a new basin that embodies a new restored community where trees dominate (new state). At the same time, ideally the new created community should have its own resistance and resilience against returning to previous degraded state (Alday & Marrs 2014).

Figure 2. Theoretical transition model between two communities. Old state is a community composed by grasses on a riverbank (red ball) and new state is a community dominated by trees (blue ball). Orange arrow represent a disturbance (management) that should produce the movement of the ball (green ball) between basins of attraction.

From a practitioner perspective, these models are good tools for examining natural systems by providing better ways of understanding changes in the restored ecosystems and, predict potential future changes (Alday & Marrs 2014). For example, when a threshold is crossed by an ecosystem under restoration it is relevant to evaluate the new restoration trajectory and improve or redesign restoration strategies. At the same time, the identification of different states and threshold between them can be used effectively in adaptive-active ecological restoration programs. In these programs, restoration actions can be fitted to the required necessities of the community at each time, accordingly, transitions between states can be accelerated or reversed. Thus, these models provide restoration practitioners and managers with better ways of understanding and communicating changes in the ecosystem after disturbances and restoration actions (Alday et al 2013).

Restoration practitioners always seek to restore mature communities in short-time by planting trees and overcoming related problems at once. However, the effectiveness of these methodologies in achieving mature riparian communities usually is not as good as expected. Among the main causes of these failures highlights invasive species colonization, lack of developed soils to sustain forest community, lack of close seeds sources or seed banks (González-Alday et al. 2009; Lee et al. 2014; Bourgeois et al. 2016, Alday et al. 2016). Creating self-sustaining communities like previous ones in these areas is a long-term process to be effective. Consequently, the implementation of adaptive-active ecological restoration programs (monitoring programs) are fundamental tools to improve the creation of long-term self-sustaining restored ecosystems.

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